

Chapter 2

VISIONS OF A SUSTAINABLE WORLD – FOR NATURE AND PEOPLE¹

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Chapter 2

VISIONS OF A SUSTAINABLE WORLD – FOR NATURE AND PEOPLE

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Chapter 2 explores visions and vision development processes for transformative changes in society. Visions are desirable future states of nature and people shaped by values and worldviews. They include defined purposes, goals and intentional efforts to attain such future states. Actors and groups of actors, shaped by contexts that determine their thinking and practices, develop visions and pathways through multiple processes. Diverse visions illuminate the interdependence of humans-in-nature for a just and sustainable world and help guide policy- and decision makers in transformations to address biodiversity loss and nature's decline. Visions assessed in **Chapter 2** come from multiple sources: peer-reviewed and grey literature, civil society initiatives and social movements, alternative economic perspectives, spiritual and religious traditions, fiction, arts, urban and rural coalitions and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. These visions address themes such as oceans, land, economy, ecosystems, technologies and rights for nature.

1 **Visions anchor pathways and are of fundamental importance in inspiring transformative change (*well established*). Given that the world is composed by diverse societies, economies, cultures and people, a range of visions are appropriate to support transformative change (*well established*) {2.3}. The 881 visions assessed in **Chapter 2** draw upon multiple sources of evidence (**Annex 2.1**) that represent transformative aspirations for desirable future states with an emphasis on peoples' relationships with nature. Five core themes emerged from these visions: 1) regenerative and circular economies, 2) community rights and empowerment, 3) biodiversity and ecosystem health, 4) spiritual reconnection for behavioural change and 5) innovative business and technology (**Figure 2.4**). These visions also cluster into four main categories: i) integrated or holistic visions that simultaneously attend to both ecological and social issues; ii) predominantly ecological visions oriented towards better human-nature relations; iii) predominantly social visions oriented towards greater equity and other social dimensions; and iv) visions with a more limited scope where specific purposes and direct and indirect drivers are not implicit (**Figure 2.3**). Diverse visions illuminate the interdependence of humans and the rest of nature for a flourishing future and encourage transformations towards a just and sustainable world {2.3.1}.**

2 **Case studies of transformative change that include explicit visions of desirable futures document the most positive impacts (*well established*). Both locally and globally relevant visions inspire transformative change (*established but incomplete*) {2.3.5, 2.3.6}. Case studies of transformative change (n=391) that include explicit visions have more positive consequences for ecological, economic and social dimensions of sustainability than those without visions explicitly stated (**Figure 2.7**). The proportion of cases of transformative potential published per year in the literature has levelled since 2015 but the absolute number is still increasing because of the overall increase in research output. Four example, indicators reflect the increase in focus on transformative change in response to biodiversity loss and nature's decline. While the amount of forest loss and land loss due to agricultural expansion has started to decline in recent years, land loss resulting from urban expansion and marine degradation due to over-exploitation of fish stocks has continued to grow, highlighting key areas of biodiversity loss and nature's decline that transformative action would help counter (**Figure 2.8**) {2.3.6}.**

3 **Intentional visioning processes for deliberate transformative change take many forms. They are more effective when four vital ingredients are present: 1) clarity of scope and purpose, 2) meaningful inclusion of people with diverse perspectives, positions, values, norms and roles, 3) use of imagination and creativity to move beyond familiar patterns, and 4) flexibility in the process to accommodate emergent ideas. Visions developed in participatory ways serve a more holistic set of purposes and address a broader array of direct and indirect drivers of biodiversity loss and nature's decline (*established but incomplete*) {2.2}. Visioning processes for inclusive, deliberate transformative change have different scopes, addressing diverse aspects of the relevant context, incorporate multiple perspectives and stakeholders inclusively with equitable voice and opportunity for engagement, involve imagination and creativity to see things differently and are flexible, adapting to the context, issues and participants, as needed. There are many potentially useful visioning processes that can be adapted to specific contexts while retaining the foundation of these four ingredients (**Box 2.1, Figure 2.2**) {2.2}.**

4 Visioning processes by Indigenous Peoples and local communities connect to fundamental rights for a desirable good life, both now and in the future. For many Indigenous Peoples and local communities, the right to self-determination – i.e., the right to make decisions about changes affecting their futures – is core to their ways of living. Food security and sovereignty, guardianship, holistic approaches, resource rights, retention and revitalization of cultural identity and respect for Indigenous ways of knowing are recurrent themes in their visioning processes and visions. Protection against external threats to Indigenous Peoples and local communities is partly addressed through striving towards these goals (*established but incomplete*) (Box 2.3) {2.3.4}. Many Indigenous Peoples and local communities express the importance of being able to retain the aspects of being and living that constitute a good life. This does not mean their visions do not change. Adaptation to change is fundamental to Indigenous Peoples and local communities and their visions regularly reflect a desire to preserve sacred concepts, ways of living and ways of being that are core to communities. This often means finding ways to defend against the many challenges these communities face, frequently from external forces. Many Indigenous Peoples and local communities do not have linear conceptions of time and deterministic visions of the future often do not resonate {2.5}.

5 Many Indigenous Peoples and local communities desire a future that responds to their interrelatedness with all aspects of life. There is diversity in their ways of being, living and knowing that builds upon oneness and interdependence (*well established*) {2.3.4}. Many Indigenous Peoples and local communities conceive people as part of nature rather than people having dominion over nature. Such conceptions imply a lesser focus on control and determinism. Conceptions of interconnection and oneness span beyond nature and people to include also the physical, spiritual and intellectual aspects of life {2.5}. Indigenous and local community concepts of transformative change are not easy to translate from Indigenous languages, oral expressions and artistic modes of communication. Indigenous Peoples and local communities provide many visions of transformative change that are related to their diversity of histories and socio-ecological, cultural and spiritual contexts from which their ideas about the future emerge {2.3.4}.

6 Visions of a better future for people and for nature are abundant, although only some visions have the potential to change the status quo and to increase the transformative capacity of initiatives in economic, social and ecological terms. Visions that are both comprehensive and supported by consequential decision makers are potentially the most

transformative (*established but incomplete*) (Figure 2.5) {2.3.2}. Such visions, even when developed by individuals and single institutions, have a greater prospect of being achieved when they include diverse perspectives and emphasize shifts that address contextually-relevant arrays of direct and indirect drivers of biodiversity loss and nature's decline and centre core social issues in a just and sustainable manner (*established but incomplete*) (Box 2.1) {2.3.2}.

A selection of visions with high transformative potential to address the underlying causes of biodiversity loss and nature's decline was assessed using criteria of resistance from the status quo and comprehensiveness (Figure 2.5) {2.3.2.1}. An assessment of visions shows that transformative change is more likely when visioning processes focus on comprehensive visions and are founded upon participatory methods that foster deliberative discussions and dialogues that bridge differences across values, cultures and cultural-historical contexts to find shared or common aspirations (Figure 2.7) {2.2.3, 2.3.5}. Visions with multiple foci have greater transformative potential. For example, an in-depth assessment conducted in Chapter 2, shows that around 62% of the visions assessed emphasize the promotion of sustainability, 63% focus on enhancing nature's contributions to people and 70% focus on enhancing quality of life. In terms of direct drivers, 71% of the visions assessed address natural resource use, whereas climate change, ocean use, pollution and land use change are addressed by 45-50% of the visions {2.3.1}. The importance of comprehensiveness and support of consequential decision makers suggests options for advancing existing and newly developed visions towards greater transformative capacity. Creators of visions that already address views, structures and practices comprehensively can emphasize the role of power dynamics for these visions to become more achievable. Creators of visions that already have low resistance from the status quo can work to bring in more comprehensiveness (i.e., the dimensions of structures and practices that are missing), to broaden their scope by dealing with more aspects that enable change. Finally, advocates who experience low resistance to comprehensive visions can advance their visions by emphasizing implementation pathways, bringing aspirations closer to reality.

7 There is an imagination gap in visioning of transformative change. This gap limits possibilities for transformative change. Among the many identified visions, most are not comprehensive and do not have high support of consequential actors, limiting the likelihood of transformative change (*established but incomplete*). Overall, the number of publications related to transformative change that refer to imagination and creativity (and related terms) is only 0.28% and 0.19% respectively of the documents in the transformative change assessment corpus of literature (referred to hereafter as assessment

corpus),² comprising 4,227,047 publications (Box 2.1) {2.2.1}. This gap limits possibilities for transformative change which break the constraints of dominant narratives and harmful systems. Addressing the imagination gap demands more comprehensive, creative and inclusive visioning processes that can include silent voices and non-human perspectives and calls for greater attention to the visions of Indigenous Peoples and local communities and underrepresented groups. Because visions vary in comprehensiveness and in resistance to their realization, their potential to inspire transformative change also varies. Visions which deal with more drivers of biodiversity loss and nature's decline, can be more impactful and easy to achieve (but not always are), while visions that are too specific do not provide the needed inspiration for change. Most visions collected represent the views of people in high-income countries; views of people in low-income countries are underrepresented in this assessment {2.3.1, 2.8.1}. New social imaginaries, such as new eco-social or natural social contracts, can shift core understandings of human-nature relationships and provide guidance for pathways to achieving them {2.4.2}.

8 Visioning processes involving collective imagining of fundamental changes in human-nature relationships are often associated with transformative change (established but incomplete). Visioning processes help people see the connections among system dimensions and processes including views, structures and practices that influence human-nature relations, sometimes expressed as social imaginaries that reflect and embody how people think about the world around them {2.4.2}. Co-creative or collaborative visioning captivates peoples' imaginations, instils hope and inspiration and supports ambitious transformative change (Figure 2.7), providing guidance on what changes are needed and how to make them. There are no formalized global scenarios yet for achieving the transformative change needed to reach the 2050 Vision of living in harmony with nature, although promising scenarios are emerging (Figure 2.5C) {2.3.2.3}.

9 Transformative visions value nature in three ways identified in the Nature Futures Framework developed by the IPBES task force on scenarios and models: intrinsic (nature for nature), relational (nature as culture) and instrumental (nature for society). Some of the more transformative visions are informed by all three value types in a balanced approach to human-nature relations. The variety of values represented in visions enables identification of diverse, actionable and context-specific pathways for just and sustainable futures to conserve biodiversity and nature (established but incomplete) (Figure 2.5) {2.3.2}.

Although some visions predominantly articulate a single nature-related value (instrumental, relational or intrinsic), most reflect at least two such values. A vision's nature-related value and its transformative potential are grounded in the reality that human survival and prosperity rests on biodiversity and ecosystem services {2.3.2}. The relative predominance of instrumental nature-related values in many visions highlights humans' inherent need to draw on natural resources for their economic survival, as well as the importance of doing so in more harmonious and regenerative ways. Visions reflecting relational values (nature as culture) and a combination of relational and intrinsic (nature for nature) values are aligned with many Indigenous and spiritual perspectives and oriented towards balancing human-nature relations in healthy ways (Figure 2.5B) {2.3.2}. The relative lack of intrinsic (nature for nature) visions, which were identified to supplement the initial analysis, suggests a realistic assessment of humans' interdependence (in dominant narratives) as part of nature for economic (instrumental) and cultural (relational) reasons.

2.1 INTRODUCTION

There is consensus in the literature regarding the need for transformative changes that deliberately address global environmental challenges,³ as discussed in Chapter 1 (Folke *et al.*, 2021; Homer-Dixon *et al.*, 2021; Richardson *et al.*, 2023). The scope and urgency of addressing biodiversity loss and nature's decline is exemplified in the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity embedded in the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework,³ adopted in December 2022 by the Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity at its 15th meeting (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2022). This framework's aspiration for "a world living in harmony with nature by 2050" identifies 23 ambitious action targets for 2030 to achieve four global biodiversity goals by 2050. The 2050 Vision for Biodiversity can be understood as a call for transformative change that encompasses multiple visions³ for achieving agreed-upon desirable futures for nature³ and people. The successful implementation of transformative visions involves diverse pathways³ across scales³ and sectors. Whereas the term "vision" is used heterogeneously in the literature (Wiek & Iwaniec, 2014), it is here defined as "descriptions of desirable future states of nature and people". Compelling visions are shaped by diverse views (Chapter 1) and values, ranging from seeing people holistically as part of nature to people being separate from nature (IPBES, 2022b; Pascual *et al.*, 2023). Visions have a wide range of scopes (Pascual *et al.*, 2023), result from diverse visioning processes and define different purposes, goals and intents to attain desirable future states. Visions may align well with

2. Corpus of literature on transformative change (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10251349>).

3. See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>).

linear conceptions of time, but a focus on a linear future is misaligned with different conceptions of the passage of time as is the case for visions of time shared among some Indigenous Peoples and local communities (IPBES, 2023a).

Compelling visions are essential to inspire deliberate transformative change towards a just and sustainable world for nature and people (Pollan, 2007). Such deliberate transformative change is essential when human influences are a global force shaping planetary ecology and nature's health³ (Dasgupta, 2021; Ellis, 2015; D. Wilson *et al.*, 2014). Most past transformations³, however, have taken place without the necessary breadth, depth and dynamics that can be achieved by the intentional use of visions (IPBES, 2019b; Lent, 2017; Toffler, 2022).

Cultural values, institutions, knowledges and technologies evolve, accumulate and diversify over time within and among societies in ways as diverse as people, cultures,³ societies and ecosystems (Lenton *et al.*, 2023). So do the aspirations, imaginaries, visions and struggles of people to shape societies and the ecologies that sustain them. Successful efforts to stop biodiversity loss and reverse nature's decline (IPBES, 2019b), anthropogenic global climate change (Pörtner *et al.*, 2022; Pörtner *et al.*, 2023) and other planetary social-ecological challenges (Folke *et al.*, 2021) depend on shifting the core narratives³ that shape important imaginaries because they are central to forming mindsets (Meadows, 1999; Milkoreit, 2017; Taylor, 2003). This shift includes the visions and values within those imaginaries that deeply influence views, for example, dominant mental models³ or paradigms (Meadows, 1999; Rook, 2013) that include how people understand and relate to the rest of nature.

In addition to vision development, content and purpose, it is essential to understand what enables visions to be widely shared and influential (effective in inspiring and shaping institutional structures and practices) for transformative change (Ellis, 2019). Widespread sharing and adoption of visions is contingent on whether they are relevant to the sociocultural contexts and worldviews,³ including those based on Indigenous and local knowledges (Harris & Wasilewski, 2004; IPBES, 2023), especially if visions are to transform human-nature relations at the planetary scale (Ellis, 2023). Visions can be linked to scenarios,³ defined as plausible descriptions of how the future might unfold based on identified conditions and specified processes of change in conditions. Scenarios describe a range of potential forward pathways, trajectories or futures, highlighting risks and opportunities associated with each (Pereira *et al.*, 2020, 2021, 2023). Pathways represent the “how to” of advancing towards desired end states, offering courses of actions evolving from the present to the future, often with mechanisms for assessment, adaptive learning and course correction.

Visions and visioning processes enable people to see how desired futures are part of a journey towards transformative change, as articulated in the broad approaches of theories and frameworks that underlie transformative change (Figure 3.2 in **Chapter 3**), rather than a means of identifying specific pathways (Bentz *et al.*, 2022). **Chapter 2** assesses inspirational visions that include shifts in views, structures and practices⁴ towards a just and sustainable world, together with an assessment of the nature of values expressed in the included visions.

2.2 STATE OF KNOWLEDGE

2.2.1 Visions and transformative change

Visions express future desired states of the world and the goals towards which deliberate changes are directed. They are important to inspire iterative transformative changes. Visions explicitly express a desired future rather than presenting a forecast. The diversity of visions that capture human-nature connections reflects the diversity of embedded values of the entities that proposed them. Given the complexities underlying visions that are grounded in a changing world, the processes of visioning,⁴ pathway development and action for change are best conducted iteratively, with the ambition to continue toward a better future (Sarkki *et al.*, 2016; Tschakert *et al.*, 2016; Wiek & Iwaniec, 2014). Guided progress from the present state toward the desired future state benefits from the identification of pathways⁵ (**Chapter 5**) anchored in a vision (**Figure 2.1**). Identified pathways support action for transformative change (Colloff *et al.*, 2021). Actors³ and actor groups (Table 1.3 in **Chapter 1**), shaped by contexts that determine their thinking and acting, develop visions and pathways using many different processes (e.g., prospective workshops, art, imagination, collective brainstorming and iterative consultations among them).

Transformative thinking entails breaking constraints imposed by dominant narratives because such constraints reinforce the status quo. Transformative thinking also entails ‘unlearning’ knowledge or de-routinising of normal habits and learning new ones (Sofoulis, 2005). The process of visioning produces new narratives of change to reframe issues and incentivize action (Wyborn *et al.*, 2020) or adopt existing relational narratives that were previously marginalized,

4. Literature review on visioning activities (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13881042>).

5. Pathways are conceptually closely related to transformative roadmaps or missions, which have been identified as necessary for transformative change (Miedzinski *et al.*, 2019). The process of working backward from a vision to determine the pathways of change can be called “back-casting” (Bruley *et al.*, 2021; McPhearson *et al.*, 2016).

including Indigenous narratives, to seek motivation, hope, aspiration and a basis for real action, and guide pathways for transformative changes. Imagination is key to cultivate new ideas and narratives, and acts as a creative force to intertwine and influence cultural roots for powerful reconfigurations of ways of being in the world (Galafassi, 2018).

Visions provide direction for actions and behaviours of actors, be they governments, communities or the private sector. The process of developing and agreeing on a vision helps to create collective identity and shared values. Positive visions about collective futures where biodiversity, nature and people thrive are influential, if not indispensable, stimuli for desirable changes (Garcia Rodrigues *et al.*, 2022). They help counterbalance fear and anxiety invoked by negative (dystopian) visions and shed light on addressing the global polycrisis.³

2.2.2 The development of visions

Visions emerge from a diverse range of people, cultures, geographies and organizations (**Section 2.3**). They vary greatly in how they are communicated and in the extent to which authors document the process leading to the development of the vision. Rationales underlying the development of visions include experienced crisis (Villasante *et al.*, 2021) but also desires for change among stakeholders.³ For example, the dance piece 'Steps for a change' (IRD, 2019), inspired by the IPBES Global Assessment of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, contains a vision of restored and thriving nature that inspires urgent action. The Bhagavad Gita communicates an empowering vision of the spirit – the reflection of the divine in human beings and action – as a clear understanding of one's duty, in the words of Lord Krishna (The Bhagavad

Gita, 2003). Visions such as these can be important sources of inspiration for transformative change.

Many published visions⁶ emphasize the vision itself and provide few details about the method for deriving the vision. For example, Kortén (2021) communicates an “ecological civilization”³ vision of a world that focuses on wellbeing and equity³ rather than wealth creation. He states that “it weaves together threads of ongoing conversations with global colleagues in which I am privileged to participate”. Such visioning processes can produce visions with high transformative potential,³ as evident in many visions examined for **Chapter 2**, indicating that there is no “one-size-fits-all” approach. Indeed, unequal or rigid participatory processes have detrimental effects because they degrade the agency³ and relations among participants, sometimes even leading to distrust and alienation (Chambers *et al.*, 2022; Nogueira *et al.*, 2021; Reed *et al.*, 2018). There is a growing body of literature on processes for creating visions (Pereira *et al.*, 2020; Wyborn *et al.*, 2021) with a focus on deliberate visioning processes. Imagination, the ability to form a mental image of certain ideas absent in reality, is a crucial aspect of the visioning process as it allows people

to think beyond the limitations of current reality and explore new possibilities (Kind, 2020).

2.2.3 Participatory processes for vision development

Participatory methods of visioning can foster deliberative discussions and help bridge different values and cultures, as well as historical and cultural contexts (Chevalier & Buckles, 2019; IPBES, 2022c). Participant selection in deliberative visioning processes needs to account for equitable representation of individuals from different social groups (IPBES, 2022b; Wiek & Iwaniec, 2014). Care afforded to ensuring that key actors’ representation is prioritized can help avoid overly complicated visions (Reed *et al.*, 2018). Participative possibilities exist in a continuum ranging from information sharing to consultation to co-production³ of transformative visions (Arnstein, 1969; Reed *et al.*, 2018). Knowledge co-production processes have been increasingly regarded as beneficial to guiding practical change for sustainable futures (Norström *et al.*, 2020). Further, ethical guidelines that emphasize values of respect, justice³ and participant welfare (Government of Canada, 2021), as well as transparency about the success or failure of previous

6. Literature review on visioning activities (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13881042>).

Figure 2.2 **Ingredients for an effective visioning process.**

The process of creating a vision is analogous to cooking a dish (adapting the metaphor used by Seixas & Davy, 2008). There are four ingredients that are essential to the dish, but the amount of each ingredient is to be adjusted to suit the circumstances.

Box 2.1 Four key ingredients for an effective visioning process.

The details of the key ingredients to develop visioning processes are described below.

Adequate **scope** of the vision is required in order to address the complex and systemic nature of biodiversity loss and nature's decline. For visions to be transformative they also need to be coherent across scales (Hölscher *et al.*, 2022). Narrowly scoped visions fail to capture the full suite of issues related to the problem at hand and too widely scoped visions exceed the interests and capacities of participants. Nevertheless, inspiring visions range from those with a distinctly local focus to those with a global focus, like the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework.

Sharing the visioning in a participatory process improves the power of the vision and promotes inclusivity (Fazey *et al.*, 2020; Pereira *et al.*, 2020; Waddock, 2024). The "Towards a Global Ethic" vision exemplifies this principle, having been supported by nearly two hundred religious and spiritual leaders from around the world. By comparison, the "Terre de Liens" vision for farmland in France has fewer participants but demonstrates the potential for groups that have sometimes been at odds (citizens, farmers and landowners) to come together around a shared vision with a narrower scope.

Imagination is a vital ingredient in creating a vision, because it allows people to move outside the patterns of existing behaviours that reinforce systemic problems (Fazey *et al.*, 2020; Galafassi, 2018; Waddock, 2024). Imaginative creativity can be encouraged within the context of a meeting that focuses on spoken and written material and can also be catalysed using alternative modes of communication, such as visual art or dance (Montuori, 1998). For example, the number of publications referring to imagination and creativity (and related terms) is 0.28% and 0.19% respectively in the assessment corpus (n = 4,227,047).⁷ While imagination is required, there may sometimes be a need for confining imaginative visions to realistic bounds as completely unconstrained creative thinking might create visions that participants find unrealistic or unattainable because they are so far outside their experience.

Flexibility is important for a successful process to respond to changing conditions, perspectives and knowledge. This ingredient has also been referred to as "adaptivity" (Wyborn *et al.*, 2020). Kim and Oki (2011) conceptualise the visioning process as requiring governance,⁸ management and monitoring to succeed. Flexibility means that the facilitators of the process (whether formally identified or not) are prepared to be appropriately responsive. Rigid adherence to a pre-conceived process risks favouring pre-conceived views.

efforts (Reed *et al.*, 2018), help ensure that marginalized social groups' or individuals' voices are equitably heard and their values and priorities included (Chevalier & Buckles, 2019; Keahey, 2021; Reed *et al.*, 2018).

While visions need to inspire hope, they also need to be feasible in order to promote agency and guide practical change (Colloff *et al.*, 2017). Ensuring inclusion of multiple values and worldviews, geographies and bioregions, biomes and other content areas involves co-produced, collaborative, participatory and transdisciplinary visioning processes. These approaches also support the development of safe spaces for the equitable weaving in of Indigenous and local knowledge (Lundquist *et al.*, 2017; Pereira *et al.*, 2020). Inclusive facilitation of visioning empowers and enhances stakeholders' and rightsholders' capacities to push for transformative change (Wiek & Iwaniec, 2014). Collaborative visioning has positive outcomes that are more immediate than the longer term change they seek to effect, including recognizing the potential contribution of ecosystems to adaptation,³ the opportunity to restructure local social-ecological systems (Bruley *et al.*, 2021) and building new relationships and understandings (Norström *et al.*, 2020).

Creating a vision is one of the fundamental steps towards transformative change. **Chapter 2** assesses diverse visions and where vision creation fits in the transformative change process. Because visioning processes are inherently context

dependent, complex, political and iterative, no one strategy will be suitable across all actors and circumstances. Success is unlikely if one implements a predetermined process, but much more likely when one engages with and responds to the circumstances specific to the place and issues of interest. A review of the literature indicates four key "ingredients"⁷ (**Box 2.1**) that help establish effective visioning processes: scope, sharing, imagination and flexibility (**Figure 2.2**).

2.2.4. Visioning in contrast to scenario development

Scenarios represent possible futures for one or more components of a system, arising from drivers of change in nature, including alternative policy³ or management options (IPBES, 2019a). Because they outline how the future may unfold, they can be used to inform visioning processes (Pereira *et al.*, 2020). Whereas prognostic and explorative scenarios do not necessarily lead to desirable futures, scenarios can also be normative (Börjeson *et al.*, 2006). Visions in such an amalgamation with scenarios, serve as normative endpoints (desired end-states) of scenarios (Otero *et al.*, 2024).

7. Literature review on visioning activities (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13881042>).

8. Corpus of literature on transformative change (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10251349>).

There are important differences between scenarios and visions. Scenarios generally describe plausible futures given a set of assumptions and contexts, but not necessarily desirable futures. While exploratory scenarios describe plausible futures, sometimes using systems³ analysis processes, visioning starts with imagining foreseeable and typically desirable futures (Boyd *et al.*, 2015; Gaziulusoy & Ryan, 2017; Sheppard *et al.*, 2011). Visions, aim to build the capacity of groups, organizations and communities, or provide insights to steer decisions and actions over longer timeframes towards those desirable futures (O'Brien & Meadows, 2001). Visions while being rooted in fundamental realities, enable the incorporation of greater ambition in attempts to break from the constraints of historic patterns (Colloff *et al.*, 2017; Muiderman *et al.*, 2020). Integration of visions as normative endpoints infuses transformative potential into scenario development, especially when such integration emphasizes comprehensiveness and possibilities for support from key actors to change the status quo (**Section 2.3.2**).

Aside from some notable exceptions, however, current scenario development struggles to imagine futures that substantially deviate from the status quo, in part because of their focus on extrapolating from present conditions (De Jouvenel, 2000). In contrast, visioning associated with transformation implies fundamental changes in how things work in social-ecological systems³. While, for example, there are currently no formalized global scenarios for achieving the transformative change needed to achieve the 2050 Vision of living in harmony with nature (IPBES, 2016, 2022c), there is a growing number of scenarios that are starting to unpack this challenge by addressing specific values of nature and some aspects of reflexive governance for a summary of social-ecological scenarios (IPBES, 2023b).

Global environmental assessments have used the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways scenarios, to highlight climate change adaptation and mitigation options. Shared Socioeconomic Pathways include different stories of future socioeconomic development, including trends in agriculture and land use (Popp *et al.*, 2017) and fisheries (Cheung, 2018). The Shared Socioeconomic Pathways framework has only one pathway (SSP1) leading to sustainability³ improvements (O'Neill, 2016). Otero *et al.* (2020, 2024) have added a new pathway (SSP0), titled Beyond Economic Growth, that is explicitly oriented towards nature and biodiversity conservation,³ transitioning humanity towards a smaller global economy, reducing materials and energy use, improving human wellbeing and opening a range of nature/ biodiversity policies. Overall, such visions and scenarios, when they use narratives to elaborate on possible futures, need to consider key social and environmental targets (O'Neill *et al.*, 2020). Considering trade-offs and synergies³ and the selective focus that specific targets represent, no single vision or pathway is likely to yield the transformative

change needed for a just and sustainable world (Ruckelshaus *et al.*, 2020). Even SSP1, the most sustainable climate scenario, does not yield strong positive nature and biodiversity outcomes (IPBES, 2019a; Pereira *et al.*, 2021; Ruckelshaus *et al.*, 2020). It identifies mainly incremental changes³ that will be insufficient to meet global biodiversity targets or achieve transformative change, underscoring the need to develop scenarios of transformative change that focus more directly on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people³ in line with SSP0 (IPBES, 2016; Otero *et al.*, 2020; Pereira *et al.*, 2020).

2.3 VISIONS ASSESSMENT

2.3.1 Characteristics of visions

To understand the transformative potential of visions, **Chapter 2** assessed existing visions that consider desirable futures for nature and people. There are numerous sources of visions; accordingly, the chapter adopted an encompassing strategy⁹ to identify and assess visions, collecting evidence for a total of 881 visions (**Annex 2.1**). The analysis of these visions has developed an understanding of existing transformative visions, their key features, relationships among them and the general and nature-specific values present in their descriptions.

The 881 visions assessed in this chapter came especially from sources in the United States of America, Spain, the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, Canada and France. In contrast, fewer visions were identified from lower-income countries. It is crucial, however, to underscore the term 'global', which highlights the intention of many of the identified visions to be applicable at a global scale (50) and transcend individual country boundaries. 150 of the 881 visions originate in multi-country initiatives and collaborations. Regionally, most visions (532) originate from the Western European and other States. The Asia-Pacific and Latin America and the Caribbean regions contribute a moderate number of visions, with 369 and 361 respectively, while 310 and 296 visions originate in Africa and Eastern Europe, respectively.

The main, sometimes multiple, purposes of the visions span a broad spectrum of sociocultural, economic and environmental dimensions. Their conservation emphasis leans towards broad issues of ecosystem and nature protection rather than species-level conservation. Concurrently, there is a strong tendency to focus on sustainability, with 546 visions dedicated to this goal. Enhancing human wellbeing is evidenced in 558 visions that focus on nature's contributions

9. Visions database analysis strategy (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14242913>).

Figure 2.3 Characteristics of 881 visions.

(A) Sentiment analysis⁹ reveals a generally positive sentiment, indicating that the overall tone of the text is optimistic, appreciative or supportive, with a median polarity score across all entries at 0.125. (B) Subjectivity analysis indicates a moderate level of subjectivity overall, suggesting that the text contains a balanced mix of factual information and opinions, emotions or beliefs, with a mean subjectivity score at 0.368. (C) Cluster analysis results visualized by a radar plot of four vision types based on K-means clustering that considered the presence of specific purposes and direct and indirect drivers associated with the 881 visions. The cluster analysis generated four groups of visions. The yellow cluster indicates “comprehensive visions” that address multiple purposes relevant for a sustainable world, as well as their direct drivers and their underlying causes. This cluster represents visions that target indirect drivers of transformative change and is broad in scope, encompassing both nature and people in the desired future state, along with the multiple drivers to be addressed in order to achieve the stated goals and targets. The green cluster indicates “ecosystem-oriented visions” that focus on conserving nature by managing the direct drivers, with less emphasis on equity, quality of life and empowerment. This cluster includes visions that target ecosystems and nature’s contributions to people, focusing on the governance of direct drivers such as land- and sea-use change, pollution, climate change, invasive alien species and natural resource exploitation. The brown cluster indicates “equity-oriented visions”, with a strong weight on human values of equity, empowerment and quality of life. It includes governance and economic factors related to natural resource exploitation. The purple cluster indicates “narrow visions” that have a more limited scope with circumscribed purposes and inadequate attention to direct and indirect drivers.

to people and 621 visions include aspirations for a good quality of life.³ The other three purposes are distributed as: i) 406 for protecting species, ii) 494 for halting decline of biodiversity and iii) 583 for protecting, restoring and sustainably using or managing ecosystems.

Natural resource³ use is the dominating direct driver of biodiversity loss and nature’s decline addressed by the visions, with 626 cases. Four drivers, climate change, ocean use, pollution and land use change, also play substantial roles, motivating between 393 and 441 visions. Concern about invasive alien species catalyses the formulation of 142 visions. Among the indirect drivers, both economic and governance factors serve as significant catalysts

for visioning, influencing 611 visions. The need for shifts in societal values is addressed by 582 visions, while technology³ and demographic changes play a role by stimulating 382 and 242 of the visions respectively.

A sentiment analysis⁹ of the 881 visions assessed the tones and perspectives that their descriptions convey (Figure 2.3). The results confirm the generally positive sentiment present in the visions, with a positive median polarity score at 0.125, which is a numerical value that indicates the sentiment expressed in the vision text, from -1 (very negative) to +1 (very positive), with 0 being neutral. Additionally, the median subjectivity score was found to be 0.368, which is a numerical value that indicates the

degree to which a piece of text is subjective or objective, with 0 being completely objective (entirely based on facts) and 1 being completely subjective (entirely based on opinions). Such a result points to a balanced presence of personal opinions and factual content in the texts. These results suggest that the descriptions of visions are generally positive and are balanced in terms of expressing beliefs and including factual information.

Descriptions of desirable futures articulated in the 881 visions reveal five important themes: i) regenerative and circular economy;³ ii) community rights and empowerment; iii) biodiversity and ecosystem health; iv) spiritual reconnection that also prompts behavioural change; and v) innovative business and technology (Figure 2.4). As the themes in the transformative change assessment vision database (hereinafter referred to as the “vision database”) indicate, addressing business, economics and technological innovations³ that are important drivers of biodiversity loss and nature’s decline would entail fundamental shifts

(Slingenberg *et al.*, 2009). These five themes are further explained in the caption of Figure 2.4. These themes also shed light in responding to the five challenges to transformative change documented in Chapter 4. To illustrate their role, five alternative economic visions¹¹ for transformative change are highlighted (Table 2.1).

2.3.2 Inspiring visions for transformative change

A subset of 44 visions in the full vision database emerged as the most inspiring, based on the key dimensions of transformative change (views, structures and practices) (Chapter 1) and additional quality criteria (Wiek & Iwaniec, 2014) (Table SM.2.2 in Annex 2.2). These visions were classified according to their transformative potential and their nature-related values (Figure 2.5). The assessment of transformative potential is based on expected resistance

11. Systematic literature review on initiatives and social movements, grey literature, alternative economic and visions (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13881161>).

10. Spiritual and religious visions (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13919783>).

Table 2.1 Five highlighted alternative economic visions.

Alternative economic visions	Description	Key References
Circular economy	The vision combines green growth, financing for nature, the bioeconomy and ‘nature-smart development’. It is designed for restorative, regenerative use of raw materials and manufactured goods. It emphasizes: 1) reusing, extending products’ service life through repair, remanufacture, restoration, ³ upgrading and retrofitting; 2) turning old goods into as-new resources by recycling materials (upcycling).	Ellen MacArthur Foundation (n.d.-b, n.d.-a, 2013); Loiseau <i>et al.</i> , (2016); Savini (2023).
Degrowth ³ and steady-state	The vision emphasizes sustainable and equitable reduction (and stabilization) of societies’ materials and energy extraction, processing, transportation and distribution, shrinking economic activity in high-income countries that is not aligned with planetary wellbeing, while potentially expanding other sectors that are, e.g., renewable or regenerative and opening possibilities of more autonomous pathways in low-income countries.	Charonis (2021); Daly (1974); Demaria <i>et al.</i> (2013); Richardson <i>et al.</i> (2023); Savini (2023).
Wellbeing for all within planetary boundaries	This vision synthesizes multiple approaches that broadly integrate social and economic thresholds so that humanity can live within planetary boundaries in better harmony with nature, ensuring a ‘safe operating space’ for humans while staying within biogeophysical planetary limits. Goals include reducing inequality, ³ enhancing social support and shifting the economic agenda away from continuous growth, while offering dignity for humans and other-than-human beings, including ecosystems and biodiversity.	Coscieme <i>et al.</i> (2019); Costanza <i>et al.</i> (2018); Eisler (2008); Fullerton (2015); Raworth (2017); Waddock (2020).
Economics of biodiversity	The vision emphasizes ‘natural capital’ defined as the value of natural resources – incorporated into economic models – along with human capital (human knowledge) to deal with ecosystem and biodiversity losses. It emphasizes humans embedded in nature, including the entire biosphere and human ingenuity focused on the common good without transgressing biosphere boundaries.	Dasgupta (2021).
Natural social contract	The vision includes economics and goes well beyond the status quo to envision a new social-ecological contract between humans and nature. It envisions societies that are more humane and fairer, less destructive to nature and people, regarding societies as social-ecological systems focused on people as members of a community and as part of natural ecosystems.	Huntjens & Kemp (2022).

from actors who benefit from the status quo, i.e., the likelihood of opposition versus support (Ajulo *et al.*, 2020; Béné & Doyen, 2018) (**Figure 2.5A**, vertical axis) – and comprehensiveness in terms of inclusion of transformative changes in views, structures and practices oriented towards achieving sustainability and equity based on **Chapter 1** (**Figure 2.5A**, horizontal axis). Together, resistance and comprehensiveness define the transformative potential of a vision. To assess the presence of nature-related values in the visions, the Nature Futures Framework (a heuristic for visioning and scenario development used here as a structural framework to facilitate grouping of visions) was divided into 7 areas (Pereira *et al.*, 2020) and visions were coded according to the nature-related values they included (**Figure 2.5**), with five additional visions added to fill a gap, explained below.

2.3.2.1 Transformative potential: resistance from the status quo and comprehensiveness of visions

Figure 2.5-A assesses the transformative potential of visions. The upper right quadrant contains visions that are more comprehensive and likely to meet low resistance, assessed overall as possessing greatest potential for transformative change. An example is the vision “wellbeing for all within planetary boundaries”. This vision motivates ongoing efforts of some cities, regions and even countries (e.g., Scotland and New Zealand) towards developing more equitable economies that operate within planetary boundaries (Richardson *et al.*, 2023; Wahlund & Hansen, 2022) (**Table 2.1**). In so doing, transformative change for biodiversity is triggered through science-policy dialogues (Otero *et al.*, 2020).

Importantly, the present assessment suggests that as visions gain comprehensiveness, they do not always generate stronger resistance from the status quo. There is no persistent trade-off between the comprehensiveness of visions and the likelihood of implementation in the constraints of the current system. These results indicate that there is room for deliberate improvement of the transformative potential of visions. Stakeholders and decision makers can improve the transformative potential of visions by following three strategies (**Figure 2.5A**), starting from the attributes of a given vision:

- **Become more comprehensive.** Visions in the upper left quadrant could become significantly more comprehensive. The vision “circular economy”, for instance, has a relatively low level of resistance to implementation from the status quo, however, its scope could be expanded to include changing views, structures and practices to achieve its ultimate transformative ends. The visions of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations and the

World Farmers Organization might likewise increase their transformative potential by adopting agroecological principles (Altieri, 2002) and, in the case of Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, by including social sustainability and equity in global fisheries (Bennett *et al.*, 2022).

- **Reduce resistance.** Visions in the lower right quadrant could become more transformative by adding specific goals, pathways and outcomes to increase their relevance for policymakers and other stakeholders. Operationalizing degrowth, steady-state, regenerative, sufficiency and other alternative economic approaches for nature and people and testing them at the science-policy interface, for example, are visions that follow this direction (Otero *et al.*, 2024). The use of scenarios showing positive trends in economic activity, equity and biodiversity indicators alongside a non-growing Gross Domestic Product can reduce the fear of governments and businesses to post-growth visions (Otero *et al.*, 2020). In parallel, a number of practices like securing independent funding and building supportive networks with like-minded institutional stakeholders can be used to avoid co-optation when upscaling radical visions like degrowth (Kaika *et al.*, 2023).

- **Make the most of a vision.** For visions in the upper right quadrant, implementation pathways could be developed and strengthened, while fully recognizing the urgent need for transformative change. The 2050 Vision included in the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, for instance, strengthens implementation of the Convention on Biological Diversity, despite resistance from some national governments and vested economic interests (Herrfahrdt-Pähle *et al.*, 2020; Zurek *et al.*, 2022).

2.3.2.2 Mapping visions onto the Nature Futures Framework

Figure 2.5-B shows the most inspiring visions mapped onto the Nature Futures Framework (Lembi *et al.*, 2020; Lundquist *et al.*, 2021; Pereira *et al.*, 2020). The Nature Futures Framework is a heuristic³ tool in the form of a triangle developed by the IPBES task force on scenarios and models, was used here as one way of capturing how inspiring visions value nature. Each Nature Futures Framework corner represents a set of specific values: i) nature for nature or valuing nature intrinsically, ii) nature as culture or valuing nature relationally and iii) nature for society or valuing nature instrumentally; with spaces in between and in the middle indicating combinations of values (**Figure 2.5-B**). The same set of 44 visions assessed for transformative potential³ (**Section 2.3.2.1** and **Annex 2.1**) was used, with the addition of five visions to fill a gap in the intrinsic value corner. These visions were mapped onto

the Nature Futures Framework triangle³ as means to feed scenario development and enrich envisioned futures with insights from science, arts, spirituality, social movements and other sources of visions.

Overall, a big group of visions tends to express instrumental values almost exclusively (lower right corner) or in combination with relational values (middle bottom). This group highlights that instrumental thinking has a strong influence even in transformative visions, recognizing the reality that humanity necessarily draws on non-human natural resources for survival. Relational values are also prominent (lower left corner) and often combined with intrinsic values (space between lower left and upper corners), particularly in spiritual, agroecological and collaborative visions. The placement of three key intergovernmental visions (the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, the Convention on Biological Diversity and the Vision 2050 for Biodiversity included in the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework) suggests there has been an evolution of natures' values over time. While the Convention on Biological Diversity falls between instrumental and intrinsic values, the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development is coded mostly as instrumental, also expressing some relational and intrinsic values. The 2050 Vision for Biodiversity falls squarely in the centre of all three values (**Figure 2.5**), similar to other visions like “wellbeing for all within planetary boundaries”, “biophilic cities” and “self-realization saves humans and nature”. These placements show that it is possible to reconcile these three values of nature and their associated visions in potentially transformative ways. The intersection of instrumental, relational and intrinsic values has not previously been considered in visions that have been generated using the Nature Futures Framework (Durán *et al.*, 2023). Results reported here are a first step to filling this gap, although the link between centrality **Figure 2.5-B** and transformative potential in **Figure 2.5-A** has not been tested.

In a parallel analysis, transformative human-nature visions were collected from social media¹² and similarly mapped on the Nature Futures Framework (**Annex 2.1**). Visions located in the Nature for Society corner of the framework capturing instrumental values, e.g., related to mining, shipping, tourism and fashion industries, were found to be more likely to operationalize sustainability discourses³ for marketing purposes, implying higher greenwashing³ potential.

2.3.2.3 Pathways to vision endpoints

A pathway to transformation is defined as a strategy for reaching a desired future based on a recognizable body of sustainability thinking and practice, driven by an identifiable coalition of researchers, practitioners and advocates (IPBES, 2022a). Pathways are particular directions of intervention, change and power³ relations (Leach *et al.*, 2010; Scoones *et al.*, 2015). Pathways that have been more marginalized or colonised than mainstream alternatives also move towards addressing the challenge of persistent relations of domination³ (**Chapter 4**) (Bourgeois *et al.*, 2022; Leach *et al.*, 2010; Terry *et al.*, 2024; Yusoff & Gabrys, 2011).

Different pathways are informed by plural values and knowledge systems to reach diverse future visions, but common interventions are needed to create the enabling conditions for the current system to decline (**Chapter 4**).

Figure 2.5-C depicts how pathways introduced in **Figure 2.1** can evolve and intertwine, depending on strategies used by the coalitions advancing them, which might for example include green economy, degrowth or nature protection coalitions as analysed in the IPBES Values Assessment (Martin *et al.*, 2022), illustrating how they might “land” in the Nature Futures Framework. It also illustrates that there are numerous possible endpoints within the triangle that combine different value orientations (Durán *et al.*, 2023; H. Kim *et al.*, 2023; Pereira *et al.*, 2020) and help achieve agreed global goals (**Chapter 5**). There are not yet agreed global scenarios for transformative change that identify distinct pathways with a clear set of strategies to achieve the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity (IPBES, 2023b). Following Durán *et al.* (2023), who only coded the corners and edges of the triangle, **Table 2.2** describes possible “endpoints” as human-nature values through the lens of the Nature Futures Framework, while noting that it is possible to achieve a combination of all value perspectives (**Figure 2.5-C**). In many Indigenous philosophies, relations are both dynamic and reciprocal. The use of nature for humans can itself be relational, linking to culture and oneness with nature. Thus, drawing distinctions and boundaries between these ways of being can be artificial and force Indigenous philosophies into scientific frameworks that may create misunderstanding or misrepresentation of their complexity and depth (David-Chavez *et al.*, 2024; Terry *et al.*, 2024).¹³

12. Social media analysis (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13844092>).

13. Some Indigenous Peoples, when asked, considered the original Nature Futures Framework (Pereira *et al.*, 2020) to have benefits in highlighting multiple value systems and saw it as a stepping stone to greater pluralism of values in decision-making and acknowledging that Indigenous peoples too hold multiple values for nature. There were also concerns that it did not represent holistic interconnectedness fundamental to many Indigenous cosmologies (IPBES, 2021). That is why in the updated version the Nature Futures Framework, a spiral signifying these multiple interconnections and porous boundaries is included to show there is no definitive delineation of what falls inside and outside the triangle (IPBES, 2023b).

Table 2.2 Endpoints used to generate multiple pathways.

Endpoints here are considered as collective ‘placements’ (mapping) of visions within the Nature Futures Framework according to how nature is valued and are based on the original six endpoints of Durán *et al.* (2023) and connected to the clusters of visions. Specific pathways to endpoints are examined more closely in Annex 2.3.

Vision endpoints	Description
Nature for nature (intrinsic value of nature)	People respect and value all life on Earth intrinsically and nature has a lot of urgency. This value set is characterized by setting aside vast areas of land and sea for nature’s use. There is a focus on people living in self-sustaining urban areas designed to minimize the influence of people in the biosphere, but also to ensure nature is incorporated into these settlements.
Nature for nature – nature for society (combines intrinsic and instrumental values of nature)	This interim space between the ‘nature for nature’ and ‘nature for society’ corners of the triangle aims to balance intrinsic and instrumental values for nature. Although there are not many visions coded in this area, the ones that are include the framing of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework with a fairly strong orientation towards using nature, whilst also valuing and protecting the self-regulating capacity of the biosphere as nature and natural processes provide the resilience that enables humanity to stay within planetary boundaries (Durán <i>et al.</i> , 2023).
Nature for society (instrumental value of nature)	This cluster focuses on sustainable use of nature’s contributions to people while ensuring maintenance of the key ecosystem functions that support them (Durán <i>et al.</i> , 2023). It has a strong emphasis on sustainable food systems, ³ such as agriculture and fishing and related economic interventions to enable sustainability, such as circular economies.
Nature for society – nature as culture (combines instrumental and relational values of nature)	This cluster is one of the most populated of the vision clusters and sits between the ‘nature for society’ and ‘nature as culture’ corners. Here, there is an emphasis on social-ecological restoration, nature stewardship and strong nature-society connections. People use their knowledge systems, services and technology to manage and expand the use of ecosystems and nature whilst also enhancing their culture.
Nature as culture (relational value of nature)	This cluster has a diversity of different options from many places around the world where multiple worldviews and ways of connecting to nature are recognized. Values of reciprocity, stewardship and harmony structure people’s relationships with nature at all levels, including concepts like <i>ubuntu</i> . ³
Nature as culture – nature for nature (combines relational and intrinsic values of nature)	This cluster lies between the ‘nature as culture’ and ‘nature for nature’ corners and also has a substantial number of the most transformative visions coded in Chapter 2. These visions connect to notions like <i>Buen Vivir</i> , ³ Tao and economic framings like degrowth. Biodiverse ecosystems are valued to allow traditional socio-cultural reproduction, spiritual values and connections to be re-established and new ones to be shaped. Society accommodates the dynamism of nature through both traditional and innovative lifestyles that take into consideration cultural heritage and traditional ecological knowledge (Durán <i>et al.</i> , 2023).
Nature as culture – nature for nature – nature for society (combines relational, intrinsic and instrumental values of nature)	This cluster in the middle, reflecting a combination of all three nature values, was not included in the work of Durán <i>et al.</i> (2023), however, several visions assessed here do combine all three and appear to have significant transformative potential if implemented. This cluster emphasizes a balanced relationship among the three nature values, including recognition of the dependence of humanity on nature for economic and societal resources.

2.3.3 Technologies for transformative change

Current and emerging technologies (e.g., artificial intelligence, biotechnology and blockchain) are spreading rapidly globally (Johnson & Acemoglu, 2023; Stahl & Wright, 2018) with considerable transformative potential. They are integral to dealing with many of the world’s greatest challenges (Bettencourt *et al.*, 2007; Dauvergne, 2020). Technological advances have generated enormous positive effects in driving business innovation (Morabito, 2017), scientific (Kulkarni *et al.*, 2024) and human health progress (Schwalbe & Wahl, 2020), improving efficiency

and productivity and monitoring environmental changes (Sun *et al.*, 2020). Technology, however, will not be able to automatically drive economic development (Banerjee & Duflo, 2019; World Bank Group, 2016), safeguard sustainable uses of nature (Gorelick *et al.*, 2017), or ensure that everyone has equal access to technology (Beraja *et al.*, 2023; Mirza *et al.*, 2019) (Chapter 4).

A comprehensive analysis of the occurrence of terms related to technologies in the assessment corpus on technology (about 490,191 records that intersect searches for “transformative change”, “visions” and “technology”

and their related terms)¹⁴ shows a steep increase in documents available (Figure 2.6-A). Overall, since 1992, technology-related records containing visions have become an increasingly integral part of technological development toward sustainability (Figure 2.6). The number of new publications per year as reflected in the assessment corpus on technology experienced an exponential increase since

the 1990s, particularly after 2019. Of the 490,191 works, however, only 9,157 are also in the transformative change assessment corpus of literature on case studies (referred to hereafter as case corpus; 1.87% of the corpus of literature on technology), which suggests that there is still limited knowledge about the role of technologies for driving transformative change.

Specifically highlighted is the limited attention overall to ecological issues, particularly how little knowledge exists

14. Comprehensive analysis of the assessment corpus on technology (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13881148>).

about the functioning of the deep ocean, even while there is growing demand for critical minerals such as lithium, cobalt and graphite from the ocean seafloor. The results show that, of the 3,108 marine documents in the assessment corpus on technology, only 1.22% refer to empirical cases (38). Yet, there is an increasingly positive sentiment toward extractive technologies for most countries of the world (**Figure 2.6-C**), although environmental and societal costs and benefits of extractive technologies still need to be evaluated. This lack of knowledge as well as the lack of access to clean technologies is a substantial barrier³ (**Chapter 4**) to be overcome. Technology can only affect society positively if governed by solutions based on scientific evidence and strict government regulations (Johnson & Acemoglu, 2023).

2.3.4 Visions from Indigenous Peoples and local communities

When identifying visions of positive futures for nature and people, the knowledge of Indigenous Peoples and local communities³ is key both from a perspective of justice, equity and inclusion and due to the value of their knowledge both inside and outside their own communities (Leal Filho *et al.*, 2022; Thaman *et al.*, 2013). Indigenous and local knowledge³ continues to be marginalized in many decision-making processes (Department of Conservation Te Papa Atawhai & New Zealand Government, 2020; Harmsworth & Awatere, 2013; Loch & Riechers, 2021; Ruru *et al.*, 2017). Acknowledging and addressing this reality when tackling transformative change and visions of the future, can translate to more equitable approaches to transformative change. The knowledge, values and worldviews of Indigenous Peoples and local communities can support new ways of thinking and understanding in other knowledge communities (Berkes, 2009) and drawing from Indigenous and local knowledge can support positive transformations globally (Vijayan *et al.*, 2022). With the support from contributing authors from across the world, who were either members of Indigenous Peoples and local communities or

scholars of Indigenous and local knowledge, comprehensive but non exhaustive evidence was compiled to respond to the following questions: 1) Why are visions important? 2) What are some visions of desirable futures? 3) How well does the concept of “visions of a desirable future for biodiversity and people” resonate with Indigenous Peoples and local communities?¹⁵

Examples highlighted that Indigenous Peoples and local communities are facing extreme and interlinked pressures from climate change, social change, biodiversity loss and nature’s decline and environmental crises. Many visions are not only about how life should be but also an avoidance of the negative aspects of some dominant worldviews described as “developmentalist” and “techno-determinist” (Reina-Rozo, 2022), both when they emerge locally and when they are imposed from external and dominant and populist societies. The legacies of colonial rule in many regions and current spread of dominant worldviews impact Indigenous Peoples and local communities and also intersect with many of the threats faced today (Adams & Mulligan, 2003; Arora & Stirling, 2023; Pictou, 2023; Quijano, 2007). Maintaining and making space for visions from Indigenous worldviews that incorporate Indigenous and local cultural aspirations and perspectives, language, practice, ceremony, values and ethics³ into a wider system of meaning including nature may be an important counter to these risks (Topa & Narvaez, 2022).

There is no singular vision of the future from Indigenous Peoples and local communities, because there is a wide diversity of communities with different histories and socio-ecological, cultural and spiritual contexts from which ideas about the future emerge (Gil, 2021). The idea of a singular deterministic future, which can be imagined, may be antithetical to the multiple futures which emerge from living with the constant pressures, change and adaptation that

15. Visions from Indigenous and local knowledge (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13926219>).

Box 2.2 Resonance of the concept of “visions of transformative change for nature”.

The premise of transformative visions of sustainable futures itself could result in a poor match with some Indigenous and local ways of knowing and conceptions of change and adaptation to change. Visions of the future may be inconsistent with some Indigenous and local conceptions of time, which are not always linear or deterministic (IPBES, 2022b), or may be linear but conceived in different ways such as seeing the future as unknowable, giving greater scrutiny to the past, which is knowable (Gill, 2023). Māori in New Zealand have a particular saying (*whakataukī*): ‘*Kia whakatōmuri te haere ki whakamua*’, To walk into the future our eyes must be fixed on the past.

For communities under extreme pressure, the capacity to address long-term visions may be limited by the need to address current and near-term crises. Communities at the frontline of environmental and social crises and catastrophe (Oakes *et al.*, 2015) may have the least capacity and opportunity to participate and be included in developing visions for the future and may be most at risk of imposition of visions from sources external to their communities. Finding ways to reduce the pressures on these communities such that there is capacity to consider long-term futures is important to facilitate transitions to greater equity in participation for these communities.

occurs in communities that are closely connected to nature. Many Indigenous Peoples and local communities conceive people as part of nature rather than having dominion over it, which implies a lesser focus on control and therefore determinism. It is perhaps this lesser focus on deterministic futures and a more holistic worldview across nature, society and spirituality and a focus on the communal over the individual, which leads to ideas about the future often being described in broad and overarching terms rather than individual specific needs or wants.

Some consistent themes emerged from the analysis of contributions on visions of Indigenous Peoples and local communities (**Box 2.2, Box 2.3**). These themes are all deeply interlinked and many are associated with the concept of “biocultural innovations” (Reina-Rozo, 2022) which are envisioned as the diverse forms of innovation that emerge from communities and their knowledge and practices to meet the social and environmental challenges (Falardeau *et al.*, 2019; Roskrige, 2007).

Box 2.3 Themes of visions of desirable futures from Indigenous Peoples and local communities.

Self-determination and guardianship

Transitions to and support for the conditions that allow people and communities to be cultural and environmental guardians are a key component of many Indigenous Peoples and local communities' visions for desirable futures for nature and people (Altman *et al.*, 2020; Lyver *et al.*, 2016; Reihana *et al.*, 2023; Timoti *et al.*, 2017). Many visions include more localized decision-making and governance to allow guardianship and autonomy to be enacted at local and regional levels (Falardeau *et al.*, 2019; Iosefa *et al.*, 2013; Latulippe & Klenk, 2020; Ruru *et al.*, 2017). This local governance is essential to allow biocultural approaches that aim to support biophysical and sociocultural components (including values, language and customs) of systems (Lyver, Ruru, *et al.*, 2019; Lyver, Timoti, *et al.*, 2019; Reina-Rozo, 2022) and feedbacks³ between them (Bridgewater & Rotherham, 2019). Local self-determination may also be important where global norms concerning justice differ from local notions of justice (McGregor *et al.*, 2020; Sikor *et al.*, 2019). At national and international levels, equitable participation in decision-making processes was part of many visions (Inuit Tapiriit Kanatami, 2007). This approach involves ensuring that processes to envision futures are just and fair and not only include Indigenous Peoples and local communities but are also compatible with their ways of knowing (IPBES, 2022c). Both formal and informal institutions³ can support guardianship and revitalization of informal institutions and equitable intersection with formal institutions could be important for sustainable futures for nature and people. For example, some Sàmi communities have traditionally served as stewards of seabird eggs, cloudberry and salmon (Joks, 2022). Moreover, along the Atlantic and Arctic coast, the construction of shelters for eiders producing down, has been a centuries-old practice, contributing to the designation of the region as a world heritage site in Norway (Hinderaker & Nielsen, 2022). The *sida*,³ communities in Sàmi, consisting of the people, land and the reindeer herd, together create a unit that has deep knowledge of the landscape and on how to adapt to available resources (Sara, 2001). The Sàmi “reindeer luck” consists of ethical and moral premises for a good future life and relies upon reciprocity between nature and people, and depends on respect for nature, people and spirituality (Oskal, 2000).

Holistic approaches

Visions consistently emphasize the need to address nature as an interconnected yet inseparable part of life that comprises nature and livelihoods as well as the physical, spiritual and intellectual components of life. These elements continue to reinforce the social fabric of society as part of a kinship worldview that comprises an intelligent and living nature (Harmsworth & Awatere, 2013; Timoti *et al.*, 2017; Topa & Narvaez, 2022). An all-encompassing, holistic connection to the natural world is embedded within the Sami notion of *birgenjupmi*, which reflects a long-term view for life sustenance and a moderate use of nature based on its capacity for self-renewal, for households and moderate sales for revenue (Porsanger & Guttorm, Gunvor, 2011). The separation of humans from nature and reductive views that focus only on the biophysical system have been seen as problematic visions that can cause damage (Satyal *et al.*, 2017), limit the potential for transformative political change, pose issues for self-governance and may need to be countered by more holistic eco-centric visions. The need for balance in all systems and the focus on the interconnected components of a good life or good future has been stressed repeatedly (Harmsworth & Awatere, 2013). This entails recognizing that balance challenges simplistic visions that focus on single targets (e.g., protecting land from anthropogenic stressors by excluding people), which may not resonate well with the visions of Indigenous Peoples and local communities (Büscher *et al.*, 2017).

Resource and land rights

Nature conservation has a history of dispossessing people of their lands and resources (Moewaka Barnes & McCreanor, 2019). Many protected areas³ were created under the incorrect assumption that Indigenous lands were unpopulated (M'sit No'kmaq *et al.*, 2021) with cases reported to this day (Domínguez & Luoma, 2020; Pictou, 2023). Land grabs for resources such as biofuels, oil palm, grain, rubber, timber, minerals and water also impact Indigenous Peoples and local communities (Blanco *et al.*, 2023; Siqueira-Gay & Sanchez, 2021; Yang & He, 2021). Retaining and revitalizing connection to land has been a common theme across many desired visions of Indigenous Peoples and local communities. In Latin America, the designation of rights to land as a subject of rights has also

Box 2 3

emerged in visions of desirable futures (Berros, 2021; Buah-Kwofie & Humphries, 2017; Espinosa, 2019).

Food security and sovereignty and local livelihoods

Food security, food sovereignty and local livelihoods are often closely tied to nature (Padulosi *et al.*, 2022). Against a backdrop of globalisation of food markets, the often more biodiverse food systems of Indigenous Peoples and local communities supported by their values, culture, practice, Indigenous and local knowledge and land rights are part of a vision of resilience in food systems (Hunter *et al.*, 2020; Jacobs *et al.*, 2021; McKeon, 2015; *The International Peasants' Voice*, n.d.; Van Hemert, 2023). The capacity to maintain traditional foods has been impacted by many factors including reduced availability of trusted traditional seeds, increased pressure on land and forest resources, climate change and generational shifts away from traditional agriculture and harvesting (Inuit Tapiriit Kanatami, 2019; Padulosi *et al.*, 2022). Desired futures therefore often include minimizing threats to food security and sovereignty (Falardeau *et al.*, 2019). Positive futures involve elevating the prestige of food systems of Indigenous Peoples and local communities. This elevation has been accomplished through forming scientific partnerships dedicated to documenting traits, genetic resources and nutritional qualities. In addition, knowledge sharing allows an expansion of expertise and

practice, facilitated by new platforms designed for information exchange (e.g., agroecological learning circles (Padulosi *et al.*, 2022)). For pastoralists, such as the Sámi reindeer herders, access to a diversity of habitats, plants and mushrooms and flexibility in access to these resources in different seasons, are crucial for the economy and way of life (Hausner *et al.*, 2021). For herders experiencing threats from multiple land uses, especially in relation to a green transition, there is a desire for better use of Sámi knowledge and better planning processes for securing critical ecosystem services³ (Risvoll *et al.*, 2022).

Retention and revitalization of language, culture and Indigenous ways of knowing

To integratively address these many inter-linked needs for sustaining culture, one emerging vision is the re-Indigenization of conservation (Fernández-Llamazares *et al.*, 2020, 2021; Reihana *et al.*, 2023; Ruru *et al.*, 2017). Re-Indigenization involves embracing Indigenous worldviews, learning from Indigenous values, customs, languages and concepts, learning from relational views of life and supporting decolonisation and reconciliation processes (M'sit No'kmaq *et al.*, 2021). Concepts such as “two-eyed seeing” also aim to create benefits from interweaving Indigenous ways of knowing with Western science to support environmental management and decision-making for more positive futures (Reid *et al.*, 2020).

2.3.5 Realizing transformative changes through visions

This subsection analyses 17 illustrative examples from the case study database¹⁶ that showcase transformative potential. These examples are developed by different groups of actors which engage with diverse views, structures and practices, aiming to address the four principles of transformative change indicated in **Chapter 1**. The visions behind these cases are designed to inspire transformative change to address biodiversity loss and nature's decline.

To assess the potential of visions to bring about transformative change, a joint analysis of the visions was conducted with evidence in the vision database from **Chapter 2** (n=881) and the transformative change assessment case study database (referred to hereafter as the case study database)¹⁶ (n=391). The analysis indicated that cases of transformative change that include explicit or implicit visions have more positive outcomes in ecological, economic and social dimensions (**Figure 2.7-A**). In addition, cases that included actions by Indigenous Peoples had a greater likelihood of transformative change compared to cases that did not (**Figure 2.7-B**). Finally, visions developed with higher levels of participation addressed more comprehensive sets of purposes for nature and people and more drivers of change (**Figure 2.7-C**).

16. Case study database with transformative potential and pitfalls (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10260233>).

Table 2 3 **Case studies developed by different actors with transformative potential.**

Private Sector	Social Movements	Community-led Initiatives	Government Initiatives
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Circular economy • Sustainable restaurant 360° • Nuru International • Global Fishing Watch 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WEAll (Wellbeing Economy Alliance) • H.E.A.R.T energy achieving real transformation • Rewilding Earth/Europe • Pachamama* 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Os Miñarzos Marine Reserve • Agroecological Resources Space • World Farmers Organization • Resilience lab • La Vía Campesina 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doughnut economics (Amsterdam) • Buen Vivir • Rights of nature • Galapagos marine reserve

* Is also a government initiative.

Figure 2.7 Technologies for transformative change for nature and people.¹⁷

(A) Transformative case studies with explicit or implicit visions behind them are associated with more positive socio-economic and nature's contributions to people outcomes; (B) Transformative case studies where Indigenous and local knowledge is promoted are associated with more positive socio-economic and nature's contributions to people outcomes; (C) Visions with higher levels of participation address a more comprehensive set of purposes and consider more comprehensive sets of direct and indirect drivers. A direct driver is a factor that unequivocally influences ecosystem processes and can be identified and measured with varying degrees of accuracy, whereas an indirect driver primarily serves as a catalyst, influencing or triggering changes that guide the system toward a desired future; multiple: different stakeholders involved in the visioning process; collaborative: two-way dialogue to seek input from different individuals in the visioning process. Data for panels (A) and (B) come from the transformative change assessment case study database. Values denote the following: 0 = neutral; 1=slightly positive, 2=largely positive. The values on radar plots represent the average across cases.

Socio-economic outcomes include 1.1: good quality of life, 1.2: food security/sovereignty, 1.3: water security, 1.4: gender equity, 1.5: reduction of race/religion/cultural/linguistic discrimination, 1.6: social cohesion and trust, 1.7: institutional strength, revive and

17. Visions database analysis strategy (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14242913>).

Figure 2 7

social participation, 1.8: power equity, 1.9: recognition of rights and values, 1.10: Indigenous Peoples and local communities' inclusion, 1.11: freedom to exercise ritual/spirituality, 1.12: access to recreation and leisure, 1.13: enjoyment of natural beauty, 1.14: promotion of a rights-based approach, 1.15: housing and shelter, 1.16: access to land/sea, 1.17: access to basic services and infrastructure, 1.18: access to knowledge and education, 1.19: access to health, 1.20: employment and job quality, 1.21: reduction of inequality/fair wealth distribution, 1.22: poverty reduction, 1.23: conservation of the productive capacity/resilience of the ecosystem.

Nature's contributions to people outcomes include 2.1: habitat creation and maintenance, 2.2: pollination and dispersal of seeds, 2.3: regulation of air quality, 2.4: regulation of climate, 2.5: regulation of ocean acidification, 2.6: regulation of freshwater quantity, 2.7: regulation of freshwater quality, 2.8: formulation and protection of soils, 2.9: regulation of hazards and extreme events, 2.10: regulation of detrimental organisms, 2.11: energy, 2.12: food and feed, 2.13: materials and assistance, 2.14: medicinal and genetic resources, 2.15: learning and inspiration, 2.16: experiences, 2.17: supporting identities, 2.18: maintenance of options.

Data for panel (C) comes from the vision database in which 0 indicates absence and 1 indicates presence, the values on the radar plot represent the average across visions.

2.3.6 Global analysis of case studies and use of quantitative indicators

A global analysis of initiatives (case studies) with transformative potential based on the assessment corpus¹⁸ (4,227,047 million documents) (see **Chapter 1** for the

18. Corpus of literature on transformative change (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10251349>).

introduction of the corpus) illustrates societal responses to major trends in biodiversity loss and nature's decline (forest loss, expansion of agriculture and urban lands and fish stocks decline) (**Figure 2.8**).

According to this analysis, the proportion of new cases with transformative potential published per year has levelled since about 2015. Taking into consideration the overall increase of research output, the absolute number is still increasing.

Figure 2 8 **Transformative change literature compared to indicators of factors detrimental to biodiversity.**

Forest loss index (green line), agriculture expansion index (orange) and urban expansion index (brown line), collapsed and overexploited fish index (turquoise line) and new cases in the assessment corpus¹⁸ (bars). Larger index values indicate a less desirable state, i.e., a lesser fraction of forest cover, larger fraction of agriculture and urban cover and a larger proportion of collapsed and overexploited fish stock. Land cover and land use data after 2015 uses higher resolution imagery.

Land loss resulting from agriculture and urban expansion and over-exploitation of fish stocks have continued to grow, highlighting key areas of biodiversity loss and nature's decline that transformative change could help improve.

2.4 IMPLICATIONS OF VISIONS FOR TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGES

2.4.1 Implications for sectors and subsystems

This assessment of visions highlights the potential for policymakers and citizens alike to adopt comprehensive and feasible transformative change approaches oriented towards equity and sustainability based on diverse visions for multiple sectors and subsystems. **Chapter 2** argues that visions can be powerful guides to achieving collectively desired futures; however, they remain just that – guides – unless supported by relevant and powerful policy frameworks, accompanied by shifts in societal views, structures and practices. Policy suited to local conditions and circumstances has the potential to achieve transformative visions and ensure that the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, the Sustainable Development Goals³ and significant shifts in economic thinking and practice are fully implemented. Transformation to achieve visions underlying these frameworks encompasses changes in all aspects of how humans live on and treat the Earth and its biodiversity in the future, that is, in how, for example, agriculture, forestry, land management, urban and rural development, marine/ocean ecosystems and economies are governed. As the following chapters highlight, considerable courage, foresight, imagination and collaboration, as well as innovative policies underpin shifts in policy and associated citizen behaviours, changes in economic practices and transformation of human-nature relationships.

The intersection of the social, cultural, economic and environmental components of any system is highlighted and emphasis placed on feedback mechanisms among them (Carpenter *et al.*, 2009; Folke *et al.*, 2004; Liu *et al.*, 2007; Ostrom, 2007). The assessment of visions from different sources emphasizes the interrelationship of the socioeconomic subsystems of societies and the natural environment. Socioeconomic systems include resource users (e.g., businesses, pastoralists, fishers and forest-dependent smallholders) and governance systems (e.g., markets, economic and political institutions). Environmental subsystems can include resource systems (e.g., forests, pasture, water), resource units (e.g., forage, fish) and the biophysical context (e.g., climate). Different visions of transformative change can have implications for different

components or the whole social-ecological system. On the one hand, envisioned changes in the socioeconomic subsystems can affect environmental outcomes. On the other hand, changes in environmental dynamics affect socioeconomic outcomes.

Integrative framing and thinking, but also transdisciplinary partnerships with Indigenous wisdom keepers and local knowledge holders have been shown to provide potential to achieve transformative change (Kassam *et al.*, 2021). People engaged in farming, herding, fishing, gathering, hunting and other ecological professions are communities of practice who contribute to the co-generation of knowledge with scholarly communities from different disciplines. Scholars and practitioners have generated visions and knowledge that can support adaptation and anticipatory capacity-building in response to changes in nature and ecosystem services. Such efforts can mean close collaboration with communities throughout the research process and to include their nuanced knowledges in order to co-generate new knowledge to address priorities and shift views, structures and practices that may prevent a just transformation for conserving nature and ecosystem services towards a flourishing world.

2.4.2 Eco-social imaginaries

Visions inform imaginaries that people use to understand the world. A social imaginary is a set of already existing, widely accepted ideas that influences and structures how people envision the present and the future (Taylor, 2003). Social imaginaries express social contracts that evolve in collective processes from key agendas articulated in the public and cultural spheres (Huntjens, 2021; Huntjens & Kemp, 2022; Mohamed & Huntjens, 2023). Today, a new discourse is emerging that proposes eco-social contracts or imaginaries addressing the almost exclusively human-centred foundation of current economies and societies (Bogert *et al.*, 2022; Huntjens, 2021; Huntjens & Kemp, 2022; Kempf & Hujo, 2022; Norton & Greenfield, 2023; UNRISD, 2022). The United Nations Research Institute for Social Development established the Global Research and Action Platform for a New Eco-Social Contract in 2021, with Green Economy Coalition and more than 350 participating organizations, including the United Nations, civil society, private sector, academia and journalists to drive understanding of a natural social contract (Huntjens, 2021; Huntjens *et al.*, 2023; Huntjens & Kemp, 2022), or eco-social contract (Gough, 2022; Kempf & Hujo, 2022; Krause *et al.*, 2022; Mohamed & Huntjens, 2023; UNRISD, 2022). A natural social contract provides eco-social perspectives that understand that humans are part of and fully interdependent with nature for all they have, do, consume, wear and inhabit (Huntjens & Kemp, 2022). A natural social contract envisions transforming societies towards greater equity and wellbeing

for all beings, including social or informal institutions and formal institutions like governments, policies and designation of rights. The goal is to develop economies and societies that serve all of life and use regenerative practices that preserve biodiversity and nature (Buckton *et al.*, 2023; Huntjens & Kemp, 2022).

New eco-social imaginaries can inform visioning processes with the transformative potential to change mindsets³ and ultimately behaviours (views and practices) needed for transformative change (Meadows, 1999). That includes revisiting much Indigenous and local knowledge to see humans as part of nature. Diverse ideas include initiatives such as Wilson's advocacy for half Earth (E. Wilson, 2016), rights of nature (Berros, 2021; Putzer *et al.*, 2022), transformative ways of human and non-human nature relating through intuitive communication (Barrett *et al.*, 2017), using a regenerative lens to rethink humans as part of nature (Buckton *et al.*, 2023), narratives that tackle scalar complexities (Dürbeck & Hüpkes, 2021) and incorporating the interests of human actors in areas demarcated for conservation. These areas could include Indigenous territories, community lands, buffer zones of protected areas, conservation concessions, land for conservation offsets, various designations of government-owned forests, military lands and certified logging concessions (Mitchell *et al.*, 2018; Schleicher, 2018). Arts-based creative practices also enable the integration of diverse knowledges (Gianelli *et al.*, 2024; Tengö *et al.*, 2014), allow participants to explore what needs to be created and dismantled (Hyysalo *et al.*, 2019) and can facilitate consideration of perspectives on silent voices and other-than humans.

Given this emerging eco-social lens, policymakers might envision people-nature or eco-social relationships as starting points for eco-social imaginaries and future policy. This thinking entails a reconsideration of the drivers of human understandings, narratives and values that frame how people think about the world, institutions and practices, strategies and actions – the foundations of human-nature relationships (Chan *et al.*, 2018). It also could mean reintegrating holistic ways of knowing, including weaving Indigenous ways that approach human-nature relations differently from mainstream approaches, shifting conservation policy away from a dominant focus on territories towards whole systems approaches including economic and social elements. Eco-social imaginaries encourage learning (and teaching others) how to think holistically and relationally (Goodchild, 2021; Harris & Wasilewski, 2004; H. Kim *et al.*, 2023), thereby contributing to understanding how whole systems transform, as described throughout this assessment.

By using new imaginaries to create visions, there is potential to create a multiplicity of transformative changes across actors and sectors for a just and sustainable world.

2.5 CONCLUSIONS

Visioning has the potential to transform the world. Imaginative, collaborative and inclusive visioning processes are more likely to create transformative visions for a just and sustainable world for nature and people. Global visions show that transitioning towards a planet where both nature and people thrive is possible, but in most cases, it will need fundamental changes in mindsets and current paradigms³ about human-nature relationships, acceptance of alternative worldviews and knowledge systems and associated practices and shifts in economic and institutional structures. The findings highlight that interlinked human and environmental processes and visions shape how views, structures and practices unfold and their multi-dimensional outcomes. The potential for considering vision goals and targets collectively as powerful guides to achieve equitable and sustainable futures is evident in efforts that link across multiple Sustainable Development Goals (Obura, 2020). This potential includes integrated actions across biodiversity and climate targets and that span societal-scales as exemplified in the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity (IPBES, 2019b; Leadley *et al.*, 2022; Pörtner *et al.*, 2023). The visioning process accounts for the importance of feedback loops envisioning links among nature, nature's contributions to people and ecosystem-based approaches and human wellbeing (O'Connor *et al.*, 2021).

Compelling visions for the future are of central importance for a shift towards pluralistic, comprehensive and feasible transformative change that addresses underlying causes of biodiversity loss and nature's decline, guided by the principles³ of transformative change and that enables global sustainability. Achieving such visions means balancing relational, intrinsic and instrumental values of nature and would benefit from imaginative visioning for human and environmental well-being. Achieving the transformative changes that visions assessed in **Chapter 2** articulate will be synonymous with the goal of responding to the unsustainable trajectories of biodiversity loss and nature's decline currently under way. The subsequent chapters of the assessment show how available theories and examples provide lessons and guidance to drive transformative change (**Chapter 3**), the challenges that hinder these visions of transformative change from turning into reality (**Chapter 4**) and the array of pathways, strategies and options available to embark on the journey towards transformative change (**Chapter 5**).

2.6. KNOWLEDGE GAPS

While working to be as inclusive as possible in documenting existing evidence and knowledge about visions for sustainable futures for nature and people, different knowledge gaps were recognized, stemming from logistical constraints:

- 1) Linguistic and geographic biases: visions were primarily collected from sources available in English and to a lesser extent in Spanish and French, thereby overlooking other UN official languages (Arabic, Chinese and Russian). This gap resulted in a geographic bias that disproportionately favoured the inclusion of visions originating from Europe and North America.
- 2) Challenges in assessing transformative potential of visions: tracking the tangible impacts of visions, particularly on a global and cross-scale basis, is difficult, as many published visions do not document outcomes, although the available evidence suggests a positive link between visioning and better outcomes. Further, disentangling the role of visions from other drivers and processes in achieving outcomes is challenging.
- 3) Lack of documentation of visioning processes: there is frequently a lack of clear description of mechanisms and concrete examples on how visions were developed (e.g., power dynamics in materializing visions). Complexities associated with technology and arts make it difficult to assess how these avenues can promote and initiate visions towards transformative changes.
- 4) Bias in vision definitions: in assessing transformative change for positive futures, visions are currently defined with an emphasis on positive outcomes only, ignoring possible unintended consequences, which could lead to an overestimation of their benefits for nature and people.
- 5) There is a gap in the understanding of the relationships between the value orientation of visions and their transformative potential. Future research could explore which combinations of nature's values (intrinsic, relational and instrumental) in the Nature Futures Framework show high comprehensiveness and low resistance from status quo in different social-ecological contexts. The central area of the Nature Futures Framework triangle (implying a balance between intrinsic, relational and instrumental values in a vision) could be a particularly pertinent.

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